

Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Stock of Non-Financial Listed Companies in East Africa Securities Exchanges

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ Charles Githira ⁽²⁾ Willy Muturi ⁽³⁾ Tabitha Nasieku

⁽¹⁾ ⁽²⁾ ⁽³⁾ Department of Accounting Economics and Finance - School of Business - Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

Abstract

Stock return movements can be adopted as a measure of growth and development of securities exchange and economy. There is a need for examination of the core determinants of stock return. Currently, it was hypothesized that there is causality between firm financial characteristics and the stock return of listed non-financial characteristics. This nexus was assumed to be moderated by shareholders concentration. Panel regression modelling was adopted to analyze the data. It was found firm value, financial health, liquidity, and leverage had a positive and significant influence on the stock return of listed non-financial companies in East Africa. In addition, there was a positive and significant moderating effect of shareholders concentration on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of listed non-financial companies in East Africa securities exchange.

Keywords: Financial Characteristics, Financial health, firm value, liquidity, leverage, stock return

1.0 Introduction

The desire for evaluation of equity markets performance worldwide has been borne by premeditated needs of current and potential investors to understand stock markets return. Statistical trend analysis has shown an increase in a number of stock markets in both developing and developed economies, for example, there were only five African based stock markets in 1990, and the number had risen to 29 by 2015 (Association of Securities Exchange in Africa, ASEA, 2015). This growth cannot be attributed to numerical changes alone but a composition of several aspects which has led to the liberalization of African based markets (Yartey & Adjasi, 2007). The development of these markets is an important milestone towards attracting private investment as well as breaching world development gaps predominant in Africa.

Recent empirical research on firm financial characteristics and stock return, have adopted static model analysis to analyze multi period data (Tripathy & Ahluwalia, 2015). Failure to consider the dynamic nature of a firm yields biased and inconsistent causality of firm financial characteristics and stock return and consequently wrong statistical inferences are drawn. Moreover, the use of ordinary least squares (OLS) to examine the effect of firm characteristics on the stock return fails to consider the time variant characteristics across firms. Thus, an empirical examination on the causality of firm financial characteristics on stock return in East Africa is inevitable using panel modelling approach which includes pooled effects, random effect, and fixed effects regression approach, (Al-Salamat & Mustafa 2016; Duy & Phuoc, 2016).

There are empirical, theoretical, geographical and conceptual variations in existing findings. These variations can be attributed to an independent evaluation of each financial characteristics on the stock return of listed companies. Further, there are geographical variations which may be attributed to differences in economic and technological development. Moreover, there are changes in time which may have an influence on levels of information asymmetry, and it may ultimately influence stock return. Shareholders concentration is anticipated to moderate the influence of firm financial characteristics mainly because of directorship voting criterion, and it may trigger share trading patterns by possibilities of majority shareholders hoarding or disposing of their share in regard to information they may be having. Further, they have veto power on financing arrangement adopted by listed companies owing to their levels of engagement as either executive or non-executive directors. Hence, the main objective was meant to establish the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of listed companies in East Africa Securities Exchanges. The study was guided by the following objectives:

1. To establish the influence of firm value on the stock return of companies listed in East Africa securities exchanges.
2. To determine the influence of financial health on the stock return of companies listed in East Africa securities exchanges.

3. To examine the influence of liquidity on the stock return of companies listed in East Africa securities exchanges.
4. To establish the influence of leverage on the stock return of companies listed in East Africa securities exchanges.
5. To examine the moderating effect of shareholders concentration on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of listed companies in East Africa securities exchanges.

The study was guided by the following hypothesis:

- i. H_{01} : Firm value has no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in East Africa securities exchanges.
- ii. H_{02} : Financial health has no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in East Africa securities exchange.
- iii. H_{03} : Liquidity has no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in East Africa securities exchange.
- iv. H_{04} : Leverage has no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in East Africa securities exchange.
- v. H_{05} : Shareholders concentration has no significant moderating effect on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of companies listed in East Africa securities exchange.

2.0 Literature Review

Signaling hypotheses date back to a study by Spence (1973). This theory was arrived by Spence (1973) when they argued that whenever a company declares an increase of dividend payment, then there are prospects for superior performance. Further, empirical examination of voluntary dissemination of information to members of the public has revealed that there is significant causality between firm performance and information dissemination. Therefore those companies which continuously disseminate their information to members of the public has high chances of superior stock returns as compared to their rivals.

Dissemination of financial characteristics information during the annual general meeting through audited annual financial statements minimizes the level of risk exposure and consequently maximizes the stock return. Since there are heterogeneous investors, there is a need to disseminate information in a clear and simplified manner and discuss corporate firm performance in different periods. Moreover, the presentation of trend analysis on financial characteristics will always be an indicator of how healthy a corporation is and those investors who are interested with the company's annual returns inform of the dividend will always be sure of their benefits. The theory is appropriate for the study since financial characteristics are key indicators of a company's performance and can be used as a yardstick on how healthy a corporation is and a trigger of positive stock return.

Nwani (2015) empirically examined the applicability of Fama French, Cahart- multi factor model in (United Kingdom) the UK. The two models were adopted to examine the contribution of firm size, book to market ratio and momentum as determinants of stock return in a company listed in the UK equity market. The study relied on monthly stock data for 100 randomly selected in periods from January 1996 to December 2013. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) was used to analyze the data; results revealed firm size had no significant contribution on the six portfolios which were formed while both books to market ratio and momentum had a significant contribution on the market portfolios. It would have been paramount to use panel regression analysis to analyse panel data.

Karachi Securities exchange factors model was developed for data from 2004 to 2014 was carried out by Abbas, Khan, Aziz, and Sumraniz (2015). Six portfolios were formed by the intersection of two size portfolios (small and big), and three value portfolios (high, medium and low). Multiple regression analysis was used to regress excess monthly return against market premium, size premium and value premium (MRP, SMB, and HML). Results of the study revealed that stock return is a factor of MRP, SMB, and HML.

Acheampong and Swanzy (2016) modelling Ghanaia firms through three factor model. The study adopted panel research design and considered companies listed between 2002 and 2011. Multi regression analysis revealed that portfolio returns in Ghana are significantly influenced by stock return premium, size premium and value

premium. Although, the data was a panel in nature none of the panel data diagnostic tests were carried prior to modelling stock return using three factor Fama-French model.

A Kenyan study was carried out by Achola and Muriu (2016) to evaluate Fam and French model. A combination of six portfolios was formed, and they were sorted by both size and book to market ratio. Daily stock prices were collected for a period ranging from July 2004 to June 2014. There was a significant influence of three factor model on stock return. There was a need to examine classical modelling assumptions prior to modelling.

3.0 Methodology

Secondary data was consolidated from annual financial statements of listed companies in East Africa securities exchange from 2007 to 2017. Panel regression modelling was adopted to examine the influence of firm financial characteristics on stock return in East Africa securities exchanges as well a moderating of shareholders concentration. Prior to modelling classical assumptions were carried out to examine the robustness of the model. The data were non-normally distributed and non-homoscedastic. Consequently, regression models with robust standard errors were fitted. Multiple regression models for the study were as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \beta_3 X_{3it} + \beta_4 X_{4it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 3.1}$$

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \beta_3 X_{3it} + \beta_4 X_{4it} + \beta_5 Z_{it} + \beta_6 X_{1it} Z_{it} + \beta_7 X_{2it} Z_{it} + \beta_8 X_{3it} Z_{it} + \beta_9 X_{4it} Z_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 3.2}$$

Where Y- Stock return; X₁= Firm value, X₂= Firm health, X₃= Liquidity, X₄ = Leverage, Z= Shareholders concentration.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Listed companies can be broadly classified into financial and non-financial according to their regulations. Hence, there classified and study findings presented as shown in Table 4.1, the average stock return was 2.57% for listed non-financial companies in East Africa. The maximum return was 13.91 and minimum of -5.45. There were variations of stock return as accounted by the standard deviation of 2.41. The average firm value was 3.50, maximum 19.31 and minimum 0.04. Hence, there were wide variations in the firm value of listed non-financial companies listed in East Africa. The average financial health of listed non-financial companies in East Africa was 4.73 and minimum of 0.48 and a maximum of 18.30, which indicated wide variations in the financial soundness of listed non-financial companies. Average liquidity was 2.62, with a minimum of 0.10 and a maximum of 18.76. Which indicate despite some companies being more liquid there were others whose shares demand was very low. Average leverage and shareholders concentration were 52% which indicated that they were high dependence of debt capital and some firms were high dominated by majority shareholders.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

	SR	FV	FH	Liquidity	Leverage	SC
Mean	2.57	3.50	4.73	2.62	0.52	0.52
Median	2.11	2.63	3.83	2.01	0.52	0.49
Maximum	13.91	19.31	18.30	18.76	0.89	0.84
Minimum	-5.45	0.04	0.48	0.10	0.29	0.30
Std. Dev.	2.41	3.25	3.41	2.51	0.13	0.11
Skewness	1.48	1.85	1.52	2.91	0.37	0.45
Kurtosis	6.09	6.85	5.31	14.23	2.49	2.47
Jarque-Bera	356.95	554.33	282.22	3112.18	15.44	21.44
Probability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sum	1201.61	1632.52	2210.60	1223.48	242.97	240.89
Sum Sq. Dev.	2709.75	4910.96	5413.72	2946.94	7.99	5.55
Observations	467	467	467	467	467	467

4.2 Panel Unit Root Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

As shown in Table 4.2 the null hypothesis for non-stationarity or presence of unit roots was rejected since p values were less than 0.05 for all variables. Hence, we conclude that stock return, firm value, liquidity, leverage, financial health, and shareholders concentration were all stationary at levels. Hence, there was no need to fit regression models with lagged variables to examine the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of listed non-financial companies in EASE.

Table 4.2 Panel Unit Root Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Variable	Test	Statistic	P value
SR	Levin, Lin & Chu	-4.49	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-1.68	0.05
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	114.87	0.04
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	223.95	0.00
FV	Levin, Lin & Chu	-31.93	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-4.24	0.00
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	131.66	0.00
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	204.94	0.00
FH	Levin, Lin & Chu	-10.49	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-1.88	0.03
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	120.13	0.02
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	194.02	0.00
Liquidity	Levin, Lin & Chu	-6.34	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-1.84	0.05
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	113.49	0.05
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	170.10	0.00
Leverage	Levin, Lin & Chu	-6.70	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-3.13	0.00
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	140.07	0.00
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	319.47	0.00
SC	Levin, Lin & Chu	-6.36	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-2.86	0.00
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	130.77	0.00
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	267.80	0.00

4.3 Multicollinearity Test for Non-Financial Listed Companies in EASE

As shown in table 4.3, none of the tolerance limit coefficients was less than 0.1 or VIF greater than 10. Hence, there was no collinearity amongst firm value, financial health, liquidity, leverage, and shareholders concentration in non-financial companies listed in EASE Hence, joint examination of their influence on stock return was examined using regression analysis.

Table 4.3 Multicollinearity Test for Non-Financial Listed Companies in EASE

	Tolerance	VIF
Firm Value	0.345	2.9
Financial Health	0.412	2.426
Liquidity	0.348	2.877
Leverage	0.717	1.395
Shareholders Concentration	0.864	1.158
Mean		2.1512

4.4 Panel Heteroskedasticity Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Breusch-Pagan Godfrey (chi) test was adopted to examine the uniformity of error term. The null hypothesis stated that there was uniformity of error term variance against an alternative of non-uniformity. The null hypothesis was rejected at 5% level of significance for a model with and without moderation since p values were less than 0.05. Hence, we conclude that the error term was not homoscedastic; unmoderated model had chi-square of 66.28 and p value of 0.00 and moderated model had Chi-square 145.36 and p value of 0.00. The challenge was mitigated through fitting a regression model with robust standard errors (Baltagi, 2005).

Table 4.4 Panel Heteroskedasticity Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Model	χ^2 -Value	P value
Without Moderation	66.28	0.00
With Moderation	145.36	0.00

4.5 Panel Serial Correlation Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Woodridge serial autocorrelation test was applied, and it tested the null hypothesis that there was no first order autocorrelation. Results shown in Table 4.5 showed that test statistics for a model with and without moderation were not significant at 5% level of significance. This indicated the absence of first order serial correlation.

Table 4.5 Panel Serial Correlation Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Model	F value	P value
Without Moderation	214.65	0.286
With Moderation	385.63	0.258

4.6 Panel Cointegration Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Johansen cointegration test using trace statistics was carried out. The test hypothesized; that there was no cointegration. Results shown in Table 4.6 revealed that there were six cointegrating equations; this implied that there was a long run relationship between financial characteristics and the stock return of non-financial listed companies in EASE. Having established cointegration relationship, fully modified model was adopted in the study with the assumption that all panels were identical and short run parameters were panel specific.

Table 4.6 Panel Cointegration Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.26	369.17	95.75	0.00
At most 1 *	0.23	273.99	69.82	0.00
At most 2 *	0.18	191.20	47.86	0.00
At most 3 *	0.16	129.75	29.80	0.00
At most 4 *	0.11	73.38	15.49	0.00
At most 5 *	0.11	35.57	3.84	0.00

Trace test indicates 6 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

4.7 Panel Granger Causality Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

As shown in Table 4.7, there was no causality from firm value to stock return of listed companies non-financial listed companies in EASE. Secondly, there was no causality from a stock return to the financial health of listed companies. Moreover, most of the variables had no causality with stock return. There was unidirectional causality between liquidity and SR, unidirectional causality between leverage and SR, Unidirectional causality between leverage and SC and bidirectional causality between FV and leverage.

Table 4.7 Panel Granger Causality Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Null Hypothesis:	F-Statistic	Prob.	Conclusion
FV does not Granger Cause SR	0.90	0.41	
SR does not Granger Cause FV	2.50	0.08	
FH does not Granger Cause SR	3.97	0.02	
SR does not Granger Cause FH	0.38	0.69	
Liquidity does not Granger Cause SR	2.24	0.11	
SR does not Granger Cause liquidity	5.39	0.00	Unidirectional causality between liquidity and SR
Leverage does not Granger Cause SR	0.32	0.73	
SR does not Granger Cause leverage	8.76	0.00	Unidirectional causality between leverage and SR
SC does not Granger Cause SR	0.04	0.96	
SR does not Granger Cause SC	0.21	0.81	
FH does not Granger Cause FV	1.35	0.26	
FV does not Granger Cause FH	0.07	0.93	
Liquidity does not Granger Cause FV	1.37	0.26	
FV does not Granger Cause liquidity	1.96	0.14	
Leverage does not Granger Cause FV	3.51	0.03	
FV does not Granger Cause leverage	8.45	0.00	Bi directional causality between FV and leverage
SC does not Granger Cause FV	0.11	0.90	
FV does not Granger Cause SC	0.14	0.87	
Liquidity does not Granger Cause FH	0.90	0.41	
FH does not Granger Cause liquidity	5.89	0.00	Unidirectional causality between liquidity and FH
Leverage does not Granger Cause FH	0.46	0.63	
FH does not Granger Cause leverage	11.10	0.00	Unidirectional causality between leverage and FH
SC does not Granger Cause FH	0.11	0.90	
FH does not Granger Cause SC	0.07	0.94	
Leverage does not Granger Cause liquidity	2.53	0.08	
Liquidity does not Granger Cause leverage	4.49	0.01	Unidirectional causality between leverage and liquidity
SC does not Granger Cause liquidity	0.67	0.51	
Liquidity does not Granger Cause SC	0.19	0.83	
SC does not Granger Cause leverage	4.42	0.01	Unidirectional causality between leverage and SC
Leverage does not Granger Cause SC	0.11	0.89	

4.8 Panel Hausman Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

The choice between random effects and fixed effects as estimation model was determined using the Hausman test. Hausman test was deployed with the null hypothesis that the random effects model was preferred against

an alternative that fixed effects were preferred. Results shown in Table 4.8 rejected the null hypothesis with Chi square of 4.12155 and p value >0.05 for the model without moderation and Chi square of 4.2208 and p value >0.05 for a model with moderation. Consequently, the most appropriate model to estimate the influence of financial characteristics on stock return in non-financial listed companies in EASE was a random effect model. Similarly, the moderating effect of shareholder's concentration was examined using a random effects model.

Table 4.8 Panel Hausman Test for Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random		4.128155	4	0.3889
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.
FV	0.200285	0.217983	0.000196	0.2059
FH	0.158848	0.133151	0.000207	0.0739
Liquidity	0.385978	0.384017	0.000401	0.9220
Leverage	3.418418	3.258851	0.026966	0.3312
Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random		4.220798	9	0.8963
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.
FV	-0.011506	0.028396	0.004222	0.5392
FH	-0.055708	-0.066520	0.002812	0.8384
Liquidity	0.699269	0.663591	0.009890	0.7198
Leverage	3.774981	3.800722	0.443169	0.9692
SC	-0.021951	0.175216	0.542274	0.7889
FV*SC	0.329788	0.297850	0.011700	0.7678
FH*SC	0.388714	0.372962	0.008156	0.8615
Liquidity*SC	-0.571364	-0.523657	0.020976	0.7419
Leverage*SC	-0.467958	-0.746502	1.595486	0.8255

4.7 Pairwise Correlation for Non-Financial Listed Companies in EASE

As shown in Table 4.9, there was a positive and significant influence on stock return in non-financial listed companies in EASE ($\rho = 0.818$, p value <0.05). Secondly, there was a positive and significant influence of financial health on stock return in non-financial listed companies in EASE ($\rho = 0.759$, p value <0.05). Thirdly, there was a positive and significant influence of liquidity and stock return in USE ($\rho = 0.840$, p value <0.05). There was a positive and significant influence of leverage and stock return ($\rho = 0.606$, p value <0.05). Shareholders concentration had a positive and significant influence on stock return in non-financial listed companies in EASE ($\rho = 0.356$, p value <0.05). These findings agreed with Tripathy and Ahluwalia (2015).

Table 4.9 Pairwise Correlation for Non-Financial Listed Companies in EASE

		SR	FV	FH	Liquidity	Leverage	SC
SR	Pearson Correlation	1					
FV	Pearson Correlation	.818**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000					
	N	437	437				
FH	Pearson Correlation	.759**	.25**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000				
	N	437	437	437			
Liquidity	Pearson Correlation	.840**	.50**	.05**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000			
	N	437	437	437	437		
Leverage	Pearson Correlation	.606**	.465**	.459**	.504**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
	N	437	437	437	437	437	
SC	Pearson Correlation	.356**	.333**	.287**	.350**	.148**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	
	N	437	437	437	437	437	437

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.8 Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Stock Return in Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

The study examined the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of financial companies listed in EASE. Results shown in Table 4.10, revealed that 83% of changes in stock return of non-financial companies listed in East Africa was jointly influenced by firm value, financial health, liquidity, and leverage. The remaining percentage was accounted for by other factors excluded in the model. Also, the firm financial characteristics had a significant joint influence on stock return ($F = 550.73$, p value <0.00) and at least one of the slope coefficients was non-zero.

The first hypothesis of the study stated that firm value had no significant influence on the stock return of listed companies' non-financial companies in EASE. Results of the study revealed a positive and significant influence of firm value on stock return ($\beta = 0.22$, t statistics = 9.00, p value <0.05). This implies that a unit increase in firm value increases stock return by 0.22 while holding financial health, liquidity, and leverage constant.

The second hypothesis stated that financial health had no significant influence on the stock return of listed companies' non-financial companies in EASE. Results of the study revealed a positive and significant influence of financial health on the stock return of listed companies in NSE ($\beta = 0.13$, t statistics = 6.27, p value <0.05). This implies that unit increase in financial health increase stock return by 0.13 units while holding firm value, liquidity and leverage are constant.

The third hypothesis of the study stated that liquidity had no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed non-financial companies in EASE. Results of the study revealed positive and significant influence of liquidity on stock return ($\beta = 0.38$, t statistics = 12.32, p value <0.05). This implies that unit increase in liquidity increase stock return by 0.38 units while holding firm value, financial health and leverage are constant.

The fourth hypothesis of the study stated that leverage had no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed non-financial companies in EASE. Results of the study revealed positive and significant influence of leverage on stock return ($\beta = 3.26$, t statistics = 7.67, p value <0.05). This implies that unit increase in leverage increases stock return by 3.26 units while holding firm value, financial health and leverage are constant.

$$\text{Stock Return} = -1.52 + 0.22*\text{Firm Value} + 0.13*\text{Financial Health} + 0.38*\text{Liquidity} + 3.26*\text{Leverage} \dots\dots\dots(4.1)$$

Table 4.10 Influence of Firm Characteristics on Stock Return in Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Variable	Coefficient	Robust Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FV	0.22	0.02	9.00	0.00
FH	0.13	0.02	6.27	0.00
Liquidity	0.38	0.03	12.32	0.00
Leverage	3.26	0.42	7.67	0.00
C	-1.52	0.20	-7.58	0.00
R-squared	0.83	Mean dependent var		2.57
Adjusted R-squared	0.83	S.D. dependent var		2.41
S.E. of regression	1.01	Sum squared residuals		469.77
F-statistic	550.73	Durbin-Watson stat		2.13
Prob(F-statistic)	0.00			

4.9 Moderating Effect on the Influence of Firm Characteristics on Stock Return in Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

The study investigated the hypothesis that; shareholders concentration had no significant moderating effect on the influence of firm financial characteristics on stock return of listed companies’ non-financial companies in EASE Multiple regression was applied, and study findings reported as shown in Table 4.11; 83 % of variations in stock return was accounted for by firm value, financial health, liquidity, leverage, shareholders concentration as well as their moderated variables.

After the incorporation of shareholder concentration as the moderator, it showed that the coefficient FV*SC was 0.30; hence shareholders concentration had a positive moderating effect on the influence of firm value on stock return. The p value was greater than 0.05. This shows that the moderating effect of shareholders concentration on firm value was statistically non-significant to stock return contribution. Secondly, there was a positive and non-significant moderating effect of shareholders concentration on the influence of financial health on the stock return of non-financial listed companies in EASE $\beta=0.37$. The p value was 0.06 which was greater than the 5% level of significance. Thirdly, shareholders concentration had a significant negative moderating effect on the leverage of listed companies in Easy Africa securities exchanges. Although, shareholders concentration had a negative significant moderating effect on liquidity, $\beta = -0.52$, t statistics = -1.86. Finally, there was the negative and insignificant moderating effect of shareholders concentration on the influence of leverage on the stock return of non-financial listed companies in EASE, $\beta = -0.75$, t statistics = -0.19.

$$\text{Stock Return} = -1.58 + 0.03*\text{Firm Value} - 0.07*\text{Financial Health} + 0.66*\text{Liquidity} + 3.80*\text{Leverage} + 0.18*\text{Shareholders concentration} + 0.30*\text{FV*SC} + 0.37*\text{FH*SC} - 0.52*\text{Liquidity*SC} - 0.75*\text{Leverage*SC} \dots\dots\dots(4.2)$$

To confirm the moderating effect of shareholders concentration, moderated and non-moderated regression coefficients were compared with the marginal change of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of non-financial listed companies in East securities exchanges. If the marginalized coefficient were different with none moderated coefficients, then there was moderation. This is achieved by differentiating model 4.2, partially and incorporating the average moderating value (shareholders concentration) as follows.

$$\frac{\delta y_{i,t}}{\delta FV_{i,t}} = \beta_1 + \beta_6 SC = 0.03 + 0.30 * 0.52 = 0.186$$

$$\frac{\delta y_{i,t}}{\delta FH_{i,t}} = \beta_2 + \beta_7 SC = -0.07 + 0.37 * 0.52 = 0.1224$$

$$\frac{\delta y_{i,t}}{\delta Liquidity_{i,t}} = \beta_3 + \beta_8 SC = 0.66 + 0.52 * 0.52 = 0.9304$$

$$\frac{\delta y_{i,t}}{\delta Leverage_{i,t}} = \beta_4 + \beta_9 SC = 3.80 - 0.75 * 0.52 = 3.41$$

When the above coefficients were compared with those in model 4.1 (Stock Return = $-1.52 + 0.22 \times \text{Firm Value} + 0.13 \times \text{Financial Health} + 0.38 \times \text{Liquidity} + 3.26 \times \text{Leverage}$), they were different which signified shareholders concentration had a moderating effect on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of non-financial listed companies in EASE

Table 4.11 Moderating Effect on the Influence of Firm Characteristics on Stock Return in Non-Financial Companies Listed in EASE

Variable	Coefficient	Robust Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FV	0.03	0.13	0.22	0.82
FH	-0.07	0.11	-0.63	0.53
Liquidity	0.66	0.17	3.91	0.00
Leverage	3.80	2.03	1.87	0.06
SC	0.18	1.80	0.10	0.92
FV*SC	0.30	0.22	1.34	0.18
FH*SC	0.37	0.20	1.88	0.06
Liquidity*SC	-0.52	0.28	-1.86	0.06
Leverage*SC	-0.75	3.85	-0.19	0.85
C	-1.58	0.95	-1.66	0.10
R-squared	0.83	Mean dependent var		2.57
Adjusted R-squared	0.83	S.D. dependent var		2.41
S.E. of regression	1.00	Akaike info criterion		2.86
Sum squared residuals	456.12	Schwarz criterion		2.95
Log likelihood	-657.14	Hannan-Quinn criterion.		2.89
F-statistic	250.88	Durbin-Watson stat		2.13
Prob(F-statistic)	0.00			

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

From the findings, it can be deduced that the stock return of listed companies in East Africa is dependent on financial characteristics which are firm value, financial health, liquidity, and leverage. Further, these influences are moderated by shareholders concentration. There is for management of listed non-financial companies to continuously disseminate information on firm value, financial health, leverage, and liquidity through annual financial statements in clear format and if possible use graphical presentations to show trend analysis. Through these investors would be able to evaluate coexistence of co-movements between variables under examinations. Future scholars should evaluate other financial characteristics beyond those exercised in the current study. There is a need to adopt alternative measures of share returns.

References

- i. Al-Salamat, W. A., & Mustafa, H.H.H., (2016) *The Impact of Capital Structure on Stock Return: Empirical Evidence from Amman Stock Exchange. International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 7(9)183-196.
- ii. ASEA (2015). *Association of African Securities Exchanges Annual Report*.
- iii. Duy, N. T., & Phuoc, N. P. H., (2016). *The Relationship between Firm Sizes and Stock Returns of Service Sector in Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange. Review of European Studies*, 8 (4),210 -219.
- iv. Spence, M. (1973). *Job Market Signaling. Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 87(3)355–374.
- v. Tripathya, T., & Ahluwalia, E. (2015). *Day Long Effect of Liquidity on Stock Return: An Empirical Investigation in a Day of Political and Economic Importance in India, International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(10)202-214.
- vi. Yartey, C. A., & Adjasi, C. K. (2007). *Stock Market Development in Sub-Saharan Africa: Critical Issues and Challenges. Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu>*.